

LEXICON PHILOSOPHICUM

International Journal for the History of Ideas

Call for Papers, Thematic Issue 2026

TERMINUS

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Lexicon Philosophicum is opening a call for submissions for a thematic issue on the term ‘Terminus’ in the history of philosophy, from Aristotle to the mid-20th century. Reflection on the nature and significance of the term ‘Term’ spans the entire history of Western (and perhaps non-Western) thought. It extends beyond its immediate linguistic context to encompass interconnected logical, grammatical, and hermeneutic dimensions, establishing it as a pivotal concept in mathematics, metaphysics, and ontology. In line with the journal’s specific approach, this special issue will explore the notion of ‘term’ through the lens and the methodologies of the history of thought, concepts, and ideas.

Lexicon Philosophicum is the flagship journal of the Institute for Intellectual Lexicon and History of Ideas of the Italian National Research Council (Istituto per il Lessico Intellettuale Europeo e la Storia delle Idee, CNR-ILIESI). The journal, open access and peer-reviewed, hosts original, unpublished contributions in the fields of the history of philosophy, the history of science, and the history of ideas.

Its distinctive approach is the historical study of terms and lexica: of the words certain texts are made of, and certain thoughts are conveyed by. Particular attention is devoted to learned and specialised terminology, lexica, and translations, concerning the history of philosophy and of the disciplines more tightly connected to philosophical debates. Consequently, the term ‘Term’ itself is an element that is as fundamental and crucial to the journal’s perspective as it has been, until now, underconsidered. In the tradition of the “Lessico Intellettuale Europeo” volumes, the Latin form ‘Terminus’ has been chosen for the thematic issue title.

The journal’s distinctive approach, as presented above, should characterize the contributions to this thematic issue. The issue will include both invited and selected papers. Among the invited contributors, and the first to accept, were Vincenzo De Risi, Graziana Ciola, Colin King, Lucia Oliveri.

Deadline for submission: June 30th 2026.

To submit your paper, please follow the instructions in the following link:

<https://lexicon.cnr.it/ojs/index.php/LP/information/authors>

Contributions may be written in Italian, English, French, and German. Please refer to the journal website for submission guidelines, editorial norms, and submission checklist:

<https://lexicon.cnr.it/ojs/index.php/LP/about/submissions>

Please note that, contrary to what is indicated on the submission page, the recommended max length for this thematic issue is 10,000 words (60,000 characters).

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